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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Evaluation of some novel 4-[4-(3-chloro-2oxo-4-substituted-phenylazetidin-1-yl)phenylamino]-1,2-dihydro-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazole-5-one

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ABSTRACT

A series of eight novel 2-Azetidinones (**4a-h**) have been synthesized by cyclocondensation of various Schiff bases of 4-[(4-aminophenyl)amino]-1,5-dimethyl-2-phenyl-1,2-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one with chloroacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine. Various Schiff bases were synthesized by condensation of 4-[(4-aminophenyl)amino]-1,5-dimethyl-2-phenyl-1,2-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one with various arylaldehydes (**3a-h**). The synthesized compounds (**4a-h**) were screened for their antibacterial activity against six microorganisms: Staphylococcus aureus (Gram positive), Bacillus subtilis (Gram positive), Salmonella typhi (Gram negative), Escherichia coli (Gram negative) and fungal strain Aspergillus niger & Candida Albicans. They were found to exhibit good to moderate antibacterial activity. Among the eight derivative compounds **4e** show the good activity. The structures were confirmed by IR, ¹H-NMR and Mass spectral data.

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Introduction

The β -lactam heterocycles are still the most prescribed antibiotics used in medicine. They are considered as an important contribution of science to humanity [1]. The most widely used antibiotics such as the penicillins, cephalosporins, carumonam, aztreonam, thienamycine and the nocardicins all contain β -lactam rings [2]. The long-term use of β -lactam antibiotics exerts selective pressure on bacteria and permits the proliferation of resistant organisms [3].

A comparative study of current antibiotics with those from previous decades shows an alarming increase in bacterial resistance to β -lactam antibiotics [4]. The development of several synthetic and semi-synthetic β -lactam antibiotics by the pharmaceutical industry was due to the growing resistance of bacteria towards the β -lactam antibiotics and the need for medicines with a more specific antibacterial activity [5].

An interesting group of β -lactams are the monocyclic β -lactams, which are molecules that do not contain another ring fused to the β -lactam one. Azetidinones, which are part of the antibiotic structure, are known to exhibit interesting biological activities [6]. A large number of 3-chloro monocyclic β -lactams possess powerful antibacterial, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, anticonvulsant and antitubercular activity [7-11]. They also function as enzyme inhibitors and are effective on the central nervous system [12]. Antipyrine Derivative (APDs) was reported in literature as antitumor [13], antimicrobial [14], antiviral [15] and analgesic drugs [16].

Hence, with a view to further assess the pharmacological profile of this class of compounds, it was thought worthwhile to synthesize some new congeners of β -lactam heterocycles by incorporating the 4-aminophenyl antipyrine and azetidinone moieties in a single molecular framework. The present work deals with the synthesis of Schiff base and lactam ring, followed by their antimicrobial screening.

Experimental :

Melting points were determined in an open capillary tube and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded (in KBr) on Shimadzu FT-IR spectrometer. ¹H-NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT-NMR) using

DMSO as solvent and TMS as Internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on Shimadzu LCMS 2010A. TLC using silicagel-G checked the purity of the compound. The physical data of all derivative was given in **Table 1**.

PROCEDURE:

(Compound –1): Synthesis of 1,5-dimethyl-4-[(4-nitrophenyl)amino]-2-phenyl-1,2-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one : A mixture of 4-amino antipyrine 4.7 gm (0.05 mol) and 4-chloro nitrobenzene 2.38 (0.015) in toluene was stirred and refluxed for 3 hours. After that allowed the mixture to stand for 16 hours at room temperature [17].

(Compound–2): 4-[(4-aminophenyl)amino]-1,5-dimethyl-2-phenyl-1,2-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one: The resulting solid were then reduced in Fe/HCl mixture (1:1) to aminophenyl derivative which was filtered off and recrystallized from dichloromethane-toluene mixture in equal ratio [13]

(Compound–3) : Synthesis of Schiff Bases derivative (3a-h):

The Schiff base was prepared by reaction of equimole of 4-amino phenyl derivative (comp-2) and substituted aromatic aldehydes. Each reactant was dissolved in a minimum amount of ethanol, then mixed together and followed by addition of 2 ml glacial acetic acid. The solution was refluxed for 10 h then cooled to room temperature and poured in to ice cold water. The solid product was collected through filtration and then dried using drying oven at 80 °C. The product was redissolved in ethanol for recrystallization and then dried to give a product. Mobile phase for TLC Benzene: Chloroform (7:3) [18]

(Compound–4) : Synthesis of Azetidinone Derivative (4a-h)

To a stirred solution of substituted Schiff bases of **Antipyrine (3a –i)** (0.01 mol), triethylamine (0.02 mol) in dioxane (dry 50 ml) and monochloroacetyl chloride (0.02 mol) was added drop wise at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min and then refluxed for 8 hours. A solid was obtained on removal of dioxane which was recrystallized from a mixture of ethanol/water. Mobile phase for TLC Benzene: Ethanol (7:3) [19].

Scheme of Synthesis

Ar is :

Table 1: Physical constant data of synthesized compound IV(a-h):

Compound No	Molecular Formula	Molecular Weight	Melting Point ^o C	% Yield	R _f Value
IVa	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ ClN ₄ O ₂	458.93	230-235	45	0.56
IVb	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂	493.58	264-268	38	0.49
IVc	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ ClFN ₄ O ₂	476.93	252-256	33	0.44
IVd	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ ClN ₄ O ₃	474.93	245-248	28	0.58
IVe	C ₂₇ H ₂₅ ClN ₄ O ₃	488.96	275-278	62	0.32
IVf	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ ClN ₄ O ₃	474.93	249-251	34	0.55
IVg	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂	493.38	270-272	35	0.53
IVh	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ ClN ₅ O ₄	503.93	280-285	58	0.36

Compound I : IR (KBr cm-1): 3430-3445 & 1270-1285 (m) (N-H str), 1670.13(C=O str), **¹H-NMR (DMSO-d₆)** δ: 4.7 (1H, Ar-C-NH), 2.67 (3H, CH₃-N) , 1.91 (3H, CH₃) 7.14 (8H, Ar-

CH)₂, **MS(m/z)** : M⁺ calculated 324.33, found 325.

Compound II : IR (KBr cm-1):3370-3390 (C-NH₂), 1670.13 (C=O), 3430-3445 &1270-1285 (m)(N-H Str), **1H-NMR (DMSO-d₆)** δ : 4.7 (1H, Ar-C-NH), 2.67 (3H, CH₃-N) , 1.91 (3H, CH₃) 7.14 (8H, Ar-CH)₂ 4.7 (2H, Ar-C-NH₂), **MS(m/z)** : M⁺ calculated 294.35, found 295.

Compound IIIa: IR (KBr cm-1): 3430-3445 (m)(N-H str), 1670.13 (C=O str) 1645.40(HC=N), **1H-NMR (DMSO-d₆)** : 4.7 (1H, Ar-C-NH), 2.67 (3H, CH₃-N) , 1.91 (3H, CH₃) 7.14 (8H, Ar-CH)₂ ,8.59 (1H, N=CH), 7.62 (4H,Ar-CH), **MS(m/z)** : M⁺ calculated 382.48, found 383.

Compound IVa: IR (KBr cm-1): 3430-3445 (N-H str), 1614.13(C=O str) 1345.14(HC-N), 1778.13(C=O str of lactam ring) 804.26 (C-Cl), **1H-NMR (DMSO-d₆)** δ: 4.7 (1H, Ar-C-NH), 5.24 (1H,-N-CH-C), 5.72(1H ,C-CH-Cl), 2.67 (3H, CH₃-N) , 1.91 (3H, CH₃) 7.14 (8H, Ar-CH)₂ , 7.62 (4H,Ar-CH), **MS(m/z)** : M⁺ calculated 458.93, found 459.

Compound IVb: IR (KBr cm-1): 3430-3445 (N-H str), 1614.13(C=O str) 1345.14(HC-N), 1778.13(C=O str of lactam ring) ,804.26 (C-Cl), **1H-NMR (DMSO-d₆)** δ: 4.7 (1H, Ar-C-NH), 5.24 (1H,-N-CH-C), 5.72(1H ,C-CH-Cl), 2.67 (3H, CH₃-N) , 1.91 (3H, CH₃) 7.14 (8H- Ar-CH)₂ , 7.62 (4H,Ar-CH), **MS(m/z)** : M⁺calculated493.38 , found 494.

Compound IVc: IR (KBr cm-1): 3430-3445 (N-H str), 1614.13(C=O str) 1345.14(HC-N), 1778.13(C=O str of lactam ring) 1312.24 (C-F) , **1H-NMR (DMSO-d₆)** δ: 4.7 (1H, Ar-C-NH), 5.24 (1H,-N-CH-C), 5.72(1H ,C-CH-Cl), 2.67 (3H, CH₃-N) , 1.91 (3H, CH₃) 7.14 (8H- Ar-CH)₂, 7.62 (4H,Ar-CH), **MS(m/z)** : M⁺calculated 476.93, found 477.

Compound IVd:

IR (KBr cm-1): 3430-3445 (N-H str), 1614.13(C=O str) 1345.14(HC-N), 1778.13(C=O

str of lactam ring) 3450.34(O-H str of Phenol), 804.26 (C-Cl), **1H-NMR (DMSO-d₆)** δ: 4.7 (1H, Ar-C-NH), 5.24 (1H,-N-CH-C), 5.72(1H ,C-CH-Cl), , 2.67 (3H, CH₃-N) , 1.91 (3H, CH₃) 7.14 (8H- Ar-CH)₂ 5.4 (1H, Ar-OH), 7.62 (4H,Ar-CH), **MS(m/z)** : M⁺calculated 474.93, found 475

Compound IVe : IR (KBr cm-1): 3430-3445 (N-H str), 1614.13(C=O str) 1345.14(HC-N), 1778.13(C=O str of lactam ring) ,1210.20 (C-O str) , 804.26 (C-Cl), **1H-NMR (DMSO-d₆)** δ: 4.7 (1H, Ar-C-NH), 5.24 (1H,-N-CH-C), 5.72(1H ,C-CH-Cl), 2.67 (3H, CH₃-N) , 1.91 (3H, CH₃) 7.14 (8H- Ar-CH)₂, 3.83(3H,OCH₃), 7.62 (4H,Ar-CH), **MS(m/z)** : M⁺calculated 488.96, found 489

Compound IVf : IR (KBr cm-1): 3430-3445 (N-H str), 1614.13(C=O str) 1345.14(HC-N), 1778.13(C=O str of lactam ring) 3450.34(O-H str of Phenol) 804.26 (C-Cl), **1H-NMR (DMSO-d₆)** δ: 4.7 (1H, Ar-C-NH), 5.24 (1H,-N-CH-C), 5.72(1H ,C-CH-Cl), 2.67 (3H, CH₃-N) , 1.91 (3H, CH₃) 7.14 (8H- Ar-CH)₂5.4 (1H, Ar-OH), 7.62 (4H,Ar-CH), **MS(m/z)** : M⁺calculated 474.93 , found 475

Compound IVg :IR (KBr cm-1): 3430-3445 (N-H str), 1614.13(C=O str) 1345.14(HC-N), 1778.13(C=O str of lactam ring) 804.26 (C-Cl), **1H-NMR (DMSO-d₆)** δ: 4.7 (1H, Ar-C-NH), 5.24 (1H,-N-CH-C), 5.72(1H ,C-CH-Cl), 2.67 (3H, CH₃-N) , 1.91 (3H, CH₃) 7.14 (8H- Ar-CH)₂, 7.62 (4H,Ar-CH), **MS(m/z)** : M⁺calculated 493.38 , found 494.

Compound IVh: IR (KBr cm-1): 3430-3445 (N-H str), 1614.13(C=O str),1345.14(HC-N), 1778.13(C=O str of lactam ring) 1450 &1325 (NO₂), 804.26 (C-Cl), **1H-NMR (DMSO-d₆)** δ: 4.7 (1H, Ar-C-NH), 5.24 (1H,-N-CH-C), 5.72(1H ,C-CH-Cl), 2.67 (3H, CH₃-N) , 1.91 (3H, CH₃) 7.14 (8H- Ar-CH), 7.62 (4H,Ar-CH), **MS(m/z)** : M⁺calculated 503.93, found 504.

In-vitro Antimicrobial screening [20]

The antimicrobial activity of all the synthesized compounds (**4a-h**) were examined against different Gram-positive(Bacillus subtilis and Staphylococcus aureus)and Gramnegative (Escherichia coli and Salmonella typhii) and fungal strainsAspergillus niger and Candida albicans organisms by measuringzone of inhibition. The antimicrobial activity was performed byAgar

diffusion method at the concentration level of 200µg/ml.Ciprofloxacin and ketoconazole as standard drug at a concentrationof 200µg/ml. Nutrient agar was used as culture media forantibacterial activity and Sabouraud dextrose agar was used as culture media for antifungal activity and DMSO as control. The results of the antimicrobial activity are shown in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Zone of inhibition (mm) data of synthesized compound:

Compound	Antibacterial activity				Antifungal activity	
	B.subtilis	S.aureus	E.coli	S. typhi	A.niger	C.albicans
1a	10	12	11	09	12	13
1b	12	13	12	08	11	10
1c	11	12	12	07	13	11
1d	13	15	11	06	12	13
1e	22	19	16	16	16	18
1f	13	11	14	11	10	12
1g	11	14	13	10	12	11
1h	14	17	15	13	14	16
Cipro-floxacin 26	26	26	27	-	-	-
Ketoconazole	-	-	-	-	27	24
Control (DMSO)	-	-	-	-	-	-

Result & Discussion :

All the synthesized final compounds were first purified by successive recrystallization using appropriate solvents. The purity of the synthesized compounds was checked by performing thin layer chromatography and determining melting points. Then the synthesized compounds were subjected to spectral analysis such as IR, NMR and Mass Spectra to confirm the structures. All the analytical details show satisfactory results. The following peaks confirmed the formation of 2-azetidinones.

The peaks at 1778.13 cm^{-1} , 804.26 cm^{-1} , 1345.14 cm^{-1} in FTIR have shown the groups of C=O, C-Cl, C-N in 2-azetidinones respectively. In $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra the peaks at 5.72 ppm & 5.34 ppm for C-CH-Cl, N-CH-C groups have confirmed the formation of 2-azetidinones. All the mass spectra showed the molecular ion peaks for their respective molecular weights apart from fragmentation profile. Since our titled compounds are known to possess antimicrobial activity, the compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity by cup-plate method.

Two gram positive bacteria such as Bacillus subtilis and Staphylococcus aureus and two gram negative bacteria such as Escherichia coli and Salmonella Typhi and two fungal species such as Aspergillus Niger and Candida albicans are tested for the activities. The concentration of $200\mu\text{g/ml}$ of our titled compounds has been used. Ciprofloxacin and Ketoconazole have been used as

standards. All the compounds have shown mild to moderate activities. Among these one 2-azetidinone having methoxyphenyl at 4th position (**compd no 4e**) have shown good activity in all the species.

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